

4-Thiazolidinones : Synthesis and Fungicidal Activity of 5-Methyl-3-aryl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidinones and their Acetoxymercuri Derivatives

SHREE RAJ SINGH

Department of Chemistry, K. D. College, Basti (U.P.)

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Nine new 5-methyl-3-aryl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidinones (iii) have been synthesised by condensing various sym.diaryl thioureas (ii) with α chloropropionic acid (I) in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate in absolute ethanol. The acetoxymercuri derivatives of these 4-thiazolidinones have also been prepared by refluxing the solutions of corresponding 4-thiazolidinones and mercuric acetate in presence of ethanol and acetic acid. The fungicidal activity of the 5-methyl-3-aryl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidinones and the acetoxymercuri derivatives of some of them have been studied.

It has been shown¹ that 4-thiazolidinones and their derivatives are associated with various kinds of potential biological activities. With a view to examine the fungicidal activity, nine new 5-methyl-3-aryl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidinones have been prepared according to the following reaction.

Acetoxy mercuri derivatives of 4-thiazolidinones act as active antifungal agents^{2,3}. It was therefore considered worthwhile to prepare some acetoxy mercuri derivatives of 5-methyl-3-aryl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidinones and to examine whether they possess any fungicidal property or not.

It has been established by several workers that on mercuration of 4-thiazolidinones, the acetoxy mercuri group enters at the para or ortho position of aryl nuclei attached to 2 and 3 positions of the 4-thiazolidinone nucleus⁴⁻⁷.

Fungicidal test : The fungicidal activity of some 5-methyl-3-aryl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidinones and

their acetoxymercuri derivatives prepared during this work has been determined by the method of Horsfall⁸. The representative fungus *Alternaria solani* was used for this test. The percentage inhibition for every tested compound was calculated by the following expression and tabulated in Tables 3 and 4.

$$\text{Percentage inhibition} = \frac{(a-b)}{a} \times 100.$$

where a and b are the areas of the colony in the control plate and the test plate respectively.

Experimental

Melting points determined in open capillaries in sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected.

5-Methyl-3-p-fluorophenyl-2-p-fluorophenylimino-4-thiazolidinones : A mixture of sym. di-p-fluorophenyl thiourea (10 g), α -chloropropionic acid (6 ml), anhydrous sodium acetate (7 g.) and absolute ethanol (30 ml.) was heated on water bath under reflux for 5 hr and poured into cold water. The separated solid was filtered, washed and recrystallised from ethanol as white crystals (8.4 g.), m.p. 250°. Found : N, 8.486; S, 10.432. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{F}_2\text{ON}_2\text{S}$ requires : N, 8.805; S, 10.062%.

Details regarding the other 4-thiazolidinones (cpd. No. 1-4 and 8 & 9) prepared similarly are given in Table 1.

5-Methyl-3-o-hydroxyphenyl-2-o-hydroxyphenylimino-4-thiazolidinone

It was prepared by refluxing the mixture of sym. di-o-hydroxyphenyl thiourea (10 g), α -chloropropionic acid (6 ml.), anhydrous sodium acetate (6 g)

and absolute ethanol (25 ml) on a water bath for 4 hr. The reaction mixture was then poured into cold water and the precipitate thus obtained was collected. It was purified by dissolving in dil. sodium hydroxide solution and reprecipitated by adding the equivalent amount of dil. hydrochloric acid. The white shining solid was filtered, washed with water and dried (yield 6.7 g) m.p. 215°. Found : N, 9.244; S, 10.416. $C_{16}H_{14}N_2O_3S$ requires : N, 8.913; S, 10.191%.

The analytical data and physical properties of other 4-thiazolidinones (cpd. No. 5-7) prepared similarly are given in Table 1.

5-Methyl-3-acetoxymercuri-p-fluorophenyl-2-acetoxymercuri-p-fluorophenylimino-4-thiazolidinone

The solutions of 5-methyl-3-p-fluorophenyl-2-p-fluorophenylimino-4-thiazolidinone (2 g in 20 ml. ethanol and 15 ml. glacial acetic acid) and mercuric

TABLE 1. 5-METHYL-3-ARYL-2-ARYLIMINO-4-THIAZOLIDINONES

III

cpd. No.	Ar	Colour	Molecular formula	m.p. °C	Yield %	Analysis %	
						N	S
1	<i>p</i> -Fluorophenyl	White	$C_{16}H_{12}F_2N_2OS$	250	70	Found 8.48 calc. 8.80	10.43 10.06
2	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	Orange Yellow	$C_{16}H_{12}N_4O_5S$	81	62	Found 15.42 calc. 15.05	8.22 8.60
3	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	Yellow	$C_{16}H_{12}N_4O_5S$	88	70	Found 15.39 calc. 15.05	8.30 8.60
4	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	Yellow	$C_{16}H_{10}N_4O_5S$	164	72	Found 15.46 calc. 15.05	8.26 8.60
5	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	White shining	$C_{16}H_{14}N_2O_3S$	215	56	Found 9.22 calc. 8.9	10.41 10.19
6	<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	White turning grey on exposure	$C_{16}H_{14}N_2O_3S$	266	62	Found 8.62 calc. 8.91	10.46 10.19
7	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	„	$C_{16}H_{14}N_2O_3S$	230	70	Found 8.54 calc. 8.91	9.86 10.19
8	2, 4-Dichlorophenyl	White	$C_{16}H_{10}Cl_2N_2OS$	64	72	Found 6.32 calc. 6.66	7.21 7.61
9	<i>S</i> -Tribromophenyl	White	$C_{16}H_8Br_3N_2OS$	89	76	Found 3.42 calc. 3.70	4.64 4.23

TABLE 2. 5-METHYL-3-ACETOXYMERCURIARYL-2-ACETOXYMERCURIARYLIMINO-4-THIAZOLIDINONES

cpd. No.	Ar	Colour	Molecular formula	m.p. °C	Yield %	Analysis %		
						N	S	Hg
1	<i>p</i> -Fluorophenyl	white	$C_{20}H_{16}F_2N_2O_5SHg_2$	200	72	Found 3.58 Calc. 3.35	3.62 3.83	48.58 48.02
2	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	Yellow	$C_{20}H_{16}N_4O_9SHg_2$	112	64	Found 5.88 calc. 6.30	3.82 3.60	45.46 45.10
3	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	Yellowish	$C_{20}H_{16}N_4O_9SHg_2$	268	68	Found 6.65 calc. 6.30	3.22 3.60	45.40 45.10
4	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	white	$C_{20}H_{18}N_2O_7SHg_2$	168	54	Found 3.62 calc. 3.37	3.46 3.85	47.82 48.21
5	<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	white	$C_{20}H_{18}N_2O_7SHg_2$	187	52	Found 3.10 calc. 3.37	3.58 3.85	48.52 48.21
6	2, 4-Dichlorophenyl	white	$C_{20}H_{14}Cl_2N_2O_5SHg_2$	76	70	Found 2.64 calc. 2.97	3.72 3.41	42.38 42.79
7	<i>S</i> -Tribromophenyl	white	$C_{20}H_{12}Br_3N_2O_5SHg_2$	138	66	Found 2.43 calc. 2.19	2.90 2.51	31.16 31.50

acetate (3.5 g in 20 ml. water and 10 ml. glacial acetic acid) were heated under reflux for 30 min. The whole content was then cooled and diluted with water. The separated white solid was filtered and washed repeatedly with hot water and finally with dil. acetic acid and hot ethanol. The pure compound was obtained in fine white crystals (yield 3.8 g), m.p. 200° d : Found : N, 3.58; S, 3.62; Hg, 48.58. $C_{20}H_{16}F_2N_2O_5SHg_2$ requires : N, 3.35; S, 3.83; Hg, 48.02 %.

Physical properties and analytical data of other acetoxymercuri derivatives of 4-thiazolidinones prepared by the above method are tabulated in Table 2.

TABLE 3. FUNGICIDAL ACTIVITY OF 5-METHYL-3-ARYL-2-ARYLIMINO-4-THIAZOLIDINONES

cpd. No. as in table 1	% Inhibition at conc.		
	1 : 1000	1 : 10000	1 : 100000
1	67.5	51.4	30.6
2	69.2	54.7	22.2
3	71.3	66.4	21.6
4	70.5	54.5	20.8
5	76.4	72.2	50.2
6	78.2	74.6	53.5
7	76.4	73.3	51.2
8	81.7	78.3	54.2
9	80.4	76.5	50.8

TABLE 4. FUNGICIDAL ACTIVITY OF 5-METHYL-3-ACETOXYMERCURIARYL-2-ACETOXYMERCURIARYL-IMINO-4-THIAZOLIDINONES

cpd. No. as in Table 2	% Inhibition at conc.		
	1 : 1000	1 : 10000	1 : 100000
1	85.4	82.3	55.8
2	80.2	75.2	32.7
3	81.4	76.3	36.5
4	86.8	82.2	62.8
5	85.2	80.8	60.5
6	88.8	82.6	56.2
7	84.8	81.2	52.3

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